

The whole genome sequence of *Bacillus safensis* GMA1, a strain isolated from hot springs in Mexico.

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Abstract

The *Bacillus pumilus* group is a subset of the *Bacillus* genus that includes highly resilient species that are alike even in the 16S rDNA gene sequences and have demanded other classification methods. Bacteria from this group are known not only because of their resistance to adverse environmental conditions but also for their ability to produce extracellular enzymes of biotechnological interest. Strain GMA1, formerly classified as *Bacillus pumilus*, has shown hydrolytic activities of interest, such as protease, lipase, and cyanide dihydratase. However, other studies have demonstrated that bacteria from the *Bacillus pumilus* group also produce other biomolecules of interest, like antimicrobials and phytohormones. Here, the whole genome sequencing of *Bacillus safensis* GMA1 is announced. The genome size is 3736651 bp, distributed in 18 contigs with an N₅₀ of 890745 and 41.58% GC. The analysis of the *B. safensis* GMA1 genome may lead to the discovery of new enzymes with technological applications and other biomolecules of interest for the food, agriculture, and pharmaceutical industries.

Introduction

Bacteria from the *Bacillus pumilus* group (*B. pumilus*, *B. safensis*, *B. altitudinis*, *B. australimaris*, *B. xiamenensis*, and *B. zhangzhouensis*) have been spotted because of their notable resistance to environmental stress, e.g., drought, salt, boron, arsenic, irradiation, UV radiation, low nutrient availability, oxidizing agents and chemical disinfectants (Dobrzyński et al., 2022; Raja and Omine, 2012). Bacteria in this group cannot be differentiated entirely based only on their 16S rRNA sequences and required DNA-DNA hybridization and *gyrB* gene sequence similarity analysis (Satomi et al., 2006; Liu et al., 2013). In addition to an enhanced taxonomic classification, the analysis of bacterial genomes produces valuable information.

Genome mining involves exploring organisms' genetic material to identify genes that encode novel enzymes, secondary metabolites, and other biologically active compounds. For *B. safensis*, genome mining can uncover unique pathways and genes responsible for its remarkable abilities, including plant growth promotion, antibacterial properties, and the production of secondary metabolites (Lateef et al., 2015). These findings will have profound implications for agriculture, where *B. safensis* can be harnessed as a natural biofertilizer and biopesticide, promoting plant growth while reducing dependency on chemical inputs. Genome mining in *B. safensis* is also significant for environmental and biotechnological applications. *B. safensis* has been isolated from various environments, including extreme habitats like space equipment and mine sites. The genomic characterization of *B. safensis* strains has revealed their potential in bioremediation,

particularly in detoxifying environments contaminated with hazardous substances such as cyanide (Justo Arevalo et al., 2022). This capability is of global environmental concern, given the widespread use of cyanide in industries such as mining, where it poses significant toxicity risks.

Furthermore, identifying gene clusters through genome mining can lead to the discovery of new antibiotics and other pharmaceutical compounds. *B. safensis*, like its close relatives *Bacillus subtilis* and *Bacillus velezensis*, produces a wide range of secondary metabolites with potential industrial and medical applications (Rabbee et al., 2023).

In addition to its interesting resistance mechanisms, *B. safensis* is also a potential source of new biomolecules of biotechnological interest, such as bacteriocins and phytohormones. In addition, it has also been identified the production of enzymes to biodegrade poly(ethylene terephthalate) and petroleum, in addition to other enzymes of interest such as cyanide dihydratase, lipases, esterases, and monooxygenases (Zeng et al., 2023; Giogia et al., 2007).

In summary, genome analysis in *B. safensis* strains is a crucial endeavor that can unlock new scientific and practical applications (Lateef et al., 2015). From environmental detoxification to the development of green agricultural practices and novel therapeutics, the insights gained from exploring the genome of *B. safensis* GMA1 promise to contribute significantly to various fields, highlighting the bacterium's multifaceted potential, leading to the discovery of new lipolytic and proteolytic enzymes as well as other biotechnologically important enzymes.

Materials and Methods

Bacterial isolate

Strain GMA1 was isolated in 1994 from the hot springs field Los Azufres in Michoacán, Mexico. The strain was formerly identified as *Bacillus pumilus* GMA1 based on its 16S rDNA gene (GenBank EU391538) and was first described elsewhere (Bustos-Jaimes et al., 2010).

DNA Processing

This procedure was carried out by Microbes NG. Five to forty microliters of the cell suspension were lysed with 120 μ L of TE buffer containing lysozyme (final concentration 0.1 mg/mL) and RNase A (ITW Reagents, Barcelona, Spain) (final concentration 0.1 mg/mL), and incubated for 25 min at 37°C. Proteinase K (VWR Chemicals, Ohio, USA) (final concentration 0.1mg/mL) and SDS (Sigma-Aldrich, Missouri, USA) (final concentration 0.5% v/v) were added and incubated for 5 min at 65°C. Genomic DNA was purified using an equal volume of SPRI beads and resuspended in EB buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8.0). DNA extracted by MicrobesNG was then quantified with the Quant-iT dsDNA HS kit (ThermoFisher Scientific) assay in an Eppendorf AF2200 plate reader (Eppendorf UK Ltd, United Kingdom) and diluted as appropriate. DNA quantification and library preparation were carried out on a Hamilton Microlab STAR automated liquid handling system (Hamilton Bonaduz AG, Switzerland). Libraries were sequenced on an Illumina NovaSeq 6000 (Illumina, San Diego, USA) using a 250 bp paired-end protocol. Reads were adapter trimmed using Trimmomatic version 0.30 (Bolger et al., 2014) with a sliding window quality cutoff of Q15. De novo assembly was performed on samples using SPAdes version 3.7 (Bankevich et al., 2012), and contigs were annotated using Prokka 1.11 (Seemann, 2014).

Illumina Sequencing

Genomic DNA libraries were prepared using the Nextera XT Library Prep Kit (Illumina, San Diego, USA) following the manufacturer's protocol with the following modifications: input DNA was increased 2-fold, and PCR elongation time was increased to 45 seconds.

Results

Trimmed sequence read data and genome assembly data of *B. safensis* GMA1 has been deposited in NCBI/GenBank under the BioProject PRJNA1091635. The size of the assembled genome of *B. safensis* GMA1 is 3736651 bp, with a mean average coverage of 68.28. A total of 46 contigs were produced, and 15 of them were larger than 1000 bp, and the largest contig was 980674 bp-long. Contigs showed an N₅₀ of 890745 bp and a L₅₀ of 2. The assembled genome has 41.58% GC and contains a total of 3842 predicted genes, including 3732 protein-coding genes, 31 rRNA, and 74 tRNA genes.

A summary of the genomic features of *B. safensis* GMA1 is listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Genomic features of *B. safensis* GMA1 isolated from the hot springs field Los Azufres in Michoacán, Mexico.

Organism (taxon classification)	Bacteria; Bacillota; Bacilli; Bacillales; Bacillaceae; Bacillus
Genome size (bp)	3736651
Number of contigs	46
Contig N ₅₀ (bp)	890745
Mean coverage	68.28
GC content (%)	41.58
BioSample IDs	SAMN40602171
GenBank accession (Assembly)	ASM3803972v1
GenBank accession (Reads)	SRR28476184

Data availability

The whole sequence of *B. safensis* GMA1 genome has been deposited in NCBI/GenBank under the accession number JBBPIB000000000, BioProject PRJNA1091635, and BioSample SAMN40602171. The version of the genome reported here is JBBPIB000000000.1.

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References

- Bankevich A, Nurk S, Antipov D, Gurevich AA, Dvorkin M, et al. (2012) SPAdes: A new genome assembly algorithm and its applications to single-cell sequencing. *J. Comput. Biol.* **19**(5), 455–477.
- Bolger AM, Lohse M, Usadel B (2014) Trimmomatic: a flexible trimmer for Illumina sequence data. *Bioinformatics* **30**(15), 2114–2120.
- Bustos-Jaimes I, Mora-Lugo R, Calcagno M, Farrés A (2010) Kinetic studies of Gly28:Ser mutant form of *Bacillus pumilus* lipase: changes in k_{cat} and thermal dependence. *BBA-Proteins Proteom.* **1804**(12), 2222–2227.
- Dobrzyński J, Jakubowska Z and Dybek B (2022) Potential of *Bacillus pumilus* to directly promote plant growth. *Front. Microbiol.* **13**, 1069053.
- Gioia J, Yerrapragada S, Qin X, Jiang H, Igboeli OC, et al. (2007) Paradoxical DNA repair and peroxide resistance gene conservation in *Bacillus pumilus* SAFR-032. *PLoS ONE* **2**(9): e928.
- Justo Arevalo S, Zapata Sifuentes D, Cuba Portocarrero A, Brescia Reátegui M, Monge Pimentel C, et al. (2022) Genomic characterization of *Bacillus safensis* isolated from mine tailings in Peru and evaluation of its cyanide-degrading enzyme CynD. *Appl Environ Microbiol.* **88**(14), e0091622.
- Lateef A, Adelere IA, Gueguim-Kana EB (2015) The biology and potential biotechnological applications of *Bacillus safensis*. *Biologia* **70**(4), 411–419.
- Liu Y, Lai Q, Dong C, Sun F, Wang L, Li G, Shao Z (2013) Phylogenetic diversity of the *Bacillus pumilus* group and the marine ecotype revealed by multilocus sequence analysis. *PLoS ONE* **8**(11): e80097.
- Rabbee MF, Hwang B-S, Baek K-H (2023) *Bacillus velezensis*: A beneficial biocontrol agent or facultative phytopathogen for sustainable agriculture. *Agronomy* **13**, 840.
- Raja, C.E., Omine, K. (2012) Arsenic, boron and salt resistant *Bacillus safensis* MS11 isolated from Mongolia desert soil. *Afr. J. Biotechnol.* **11**(9), pp. 2267–2275.
- Satomi, M., La Duc, M.T., Venkateswaran, K. (2006) *Bacillus safensis* sp. nov., isolated from spacecraft and assembly-facility surfaces. *Int. J. Syst. Evol. Microbiol.* **56**, 1735–1740.
- Seemann T (2014) Prokka: rapid prokaryotic genome annotation. *Bioinformatics* **30**(14):2068–2069.
- Zeng, C.; Ding, F.; Zhou, J.; Dong, W.; Cui, Z.; Yan, X. (2023) Biodegradation of poly(ethylene terephthalate) by *Bacillus safensis* YX8. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* **24**, 16434.